

POSITIVE EFFECTS OF DROUGHT ON THE QUALITY OF AROMATIC PLANTS: IMPROVEMENT OF TOTAL PHENOLIC AND FLAVONOID CONTENTS AND TOTAL ANTIOXIDANT CAPACITY

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ABSTRACT. This study aimed to evaluate the effects of drought on the antioxidant properties and some growth parameters of mint (*Mentha x piperita* L.), basil (*Ocimum basilicum* L.), hyssop (*Hyssopus officinalis* L.), and oregano plants (*Origanum vulgare* L.). This study was carried out at the Faculty of Agriculture and Food Sciences experimental station in Sarajevo in 2024. Four water-holding capacities (WHC), namely 90% WHC, 80% WHC, 60% WHC, and 40% WHC were used as drought stress levels in this study. An experiment had a completely randomized design with three replicates and was carried out in pots in the greenhouse under controlled conditions. The total phenolic and flavonoid contents and total antioxidant capacity in the leaf extracts of the tested plants were evaluated by the Folin-Ciocalteu assay, AlCl₃ assay, and ferric reducing/antioxidant power (FRAP) assay, respectively. Drought at 60% and 40% WHC caused a decline in plant height, leaf area, and fresh and dry weight. In contrast, it increased total phenolic and flavonoid contents and total antioxidant capacity compared to plants exposed to 80% and 90% of WHC, regardless of plant species. The highest total phenolic contents (392.9 mg 100 g⁻¹), total flavonoid contents (219.9 mg 100 g⁻¹), and total antioxidant capacity through FRAP assay (3.35 mmol Fe²⁺ 100 g⁻¹), were observed in mint plants exposed to drought at 60% WHC. The results of this study point to the conclusion that the antioxidant properties and, thus, the quality of the studied aromatic plant species can be enhanced significantly by deliberately applying drought stress during their cultivation. However, this enhancement is usually accompanied by a decrease in plant growth. In this regard, for each particular aromatic plant species, it is necessary to carefully assess the advantages and disadvantages of the deliberate application of each drought level during cultivation.

Keywords: antioxidants, basil, hyssop, mint, oregano

INTRODUCTION

Aromatic plants are excellent sources of natural phytochemicals such as phenolics, flavonoids, polypeptides, isoprenoids, and other substances that may provide desirable health benefits [1]. Among the health benefits attributed to aromatic plants, their antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties are particularly well documented [2, 3, 4]. Consequently, there is an increasing interest in using aromatic plants not only as functional food ingredients but also as therapeutic agents for the treatment of various diseases [5].

Unfortunately, the synthesis of biologically active substances in plants is relatively low and depends on many factors, including the physiological and developmental stage of the plant and environmental conditions [6]. In this light, it is well known that abiotic stressors, such as drought, high and low temperatures, and ultraviolet radiations, may increase the synthesis of phytochemicals in plants. Moreover, some biologically active substances are only synthesized under specific environmental conditions [7].

Phenolic compounds constitute one of the main classes of biologically active substances in plants. These compounds can protect cellular components from reactive free radical damage, mainly due to their ability to activate antioxidant enzymes, prevent free radical formation, or promote their decomposition. Besides, phenolic compounds are known for their broad-spectrum applicability in preventing and treating numerous health disorders, such as diabetes, neurodegenerative diseases, and cardiovascular diseases. They also exhibit anti-cancer activities and have, therefore, received more and more attention in recent years.

Numerous studies have shown that the biosynthesis of phenolic compounds in plants increases significantly when plants are exposed to drought [8, 9]. This can be explained, among others, by the fact that plants, under stress conditions, accumulate a wide range of antioxidants to quench the reactive oxidative species induced by drought. Accordingly, exposure to drought could be an innovative, cost-effective, and climate-smart approach to increase antioxidant levels in plants. On the other hand, drought can greatly reduce plant growth and productivity, especially when plants are exposed to sustained drought [10]. The decrease in plant growth and productivity under prolonged drought is mainly attributable to reduced leaf expansion and impaired photosynthesis. Low turgor pressure reduces leaf area, whereas low water supply induces stomatal closure and, thus, CO₂ entry into the leaf, limiting photosynthesis. Plants have evolved several strategies to maintain a better water balance under drought, which can be considered adaptive mechanisms to increase drought tolerance. Root length increment, reduction in leaf size, leaf rolling, osmotic adjustment, and activation of cellular antioxidant defense system are some of the most important strategies adopted by plants under drought.

However, drought tolerance varies among plant species and even within species, indicating that different plants respond differently to drought. In this light, a better understanding of drought responses offers the potential to maintain or even increase plant growth and quality under drought. This study aimed to evaluate the effects of drought on the antioxidant properties and some growth parameters of mint (*Mentha x piperita* L.), basil (*Ocimum basilicum* L.), hyssop (*Hyssopus officinalis* L.), and oregano plants (*Origanum vulgare* L.). We hypothesized that plant height, biomass production, and leaf size negatively correlate with increased drought levels. We also hypothesized that exposure of plants to drought promotes the accumulation of phenolic compounds in leaves and thus improves their quality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental design and growth conditions

This study was carried out from 18 May to 20 July 2024 under greenhouse conditions at the experimental station of the Faculty of Agriculture and Food Sciences in Sarajevo. The mint, basil, hyssop, and oregano plants used in this study were purchased from a private nursery located near the experimental station, and no significant differences were observed between plants within each species in terms of vigor, size, and appearance. When the experiment started, all plants were in the pre-flowering stage.

On May 18, 2024, all plants were transplanted in 12 cm x 20 cm plastic pots (one plant/pot) previously filled with substrate Florabella (Klasmann-Deilmann, Germany). Forty-eight pots were used for each plant species. This resulted in 192 pots. All plants within each species were exposed to four different drought levels starting 10 days after transplanting. Drought levels used in this study were as follows: (1) non-stress (90% of the maximum substrate water holding capacity (WHC)), (2) mild drought stress (80% of WHC), (3) moderate drought stress (60% of WHC) and (4) severe drought stress (40% of WHC). Tensiometers (Soil Moisture Equipment Corp., Santa Barbara, USA) were used to monitor WHC. The air circulation inside the greenhouse was achieved by opening the roof vents and main door during the daytime, while

green shade cloth was used to reduce light and heat intensity during hot days. Greenhouse air temperature remained in the range of 18–27°C during the day and 15–22°C at night; relative humidity was in the range of 50–85%.

The experimental design was Completely Randomized Block Design (CRBD) with three replicates. During the experiment, the position of the pots within each block was changed every 2-3 days to minimize the effects of light and temperature gradients within the greenhouse. Plants were exposed to different drought levels for 21 days and then re-watered until harvest (July 20, 2024). For the purposes of analyzing the total phenolics and flavonoid contents and total antioxidant capacity, three fully developed leaves from each plant were collected. After sampling, leaves were dried in an oven at 40 °C for 48 h, ground into powder using an electric blender, and then stored in paper bags until analysis. The growth parameters, including plant height, above-ground biomass (fresh and dry weights), and leaf area, were also recorded.

Phenolic compounds extraction

The dried and ground leaf sample (1 g) was extracted in a 100-mL tightly capped flask with 40 ml of 50% aqueous ethanol (v/v) by maceration using an orbital shaker for 6 h. The extract was then filtered through a coarse filter paper into a 50 mL volumetric flask and then diluted to the mark with extract solution. The extract thus obtained was used for total phenolic and flavonoid content and total antioxidant activity chemical analysis.

Total phenolic content estimation

The total phenolic content was estimated by the Folin-Ciocalteu method [11] as follows: 0.1 mL of extract, 6 mL of distilled water, and 0.5 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (previously diluted 1:2, reagent: distilled water) were placed and mixed thoroughly in a test tube. The mixture was incubated at room temperature for 5 min, and then 1.5 mL of saturated sodium carbonate solution (Na_2CO_3) was added. After 15 min, the resulting mixture was assayed spectrophotometrically at 765 nm. The gallic acid calibration curve ($0\text{--}500\text{ mg L}^{-1}$) was used to determine the total phenolic content in each extract, and then the obtained values were recalculated to fresh weight ($\text{mg eq. GAE } 100\text{ g}^{-1}\text{ FW}$).

Total flavonoid content estimation

The total flavonoid content was estimated by the Aluminium chloride colorimetric assay [12] as follows: 1 mL of extract, 4 mL of distilled water, and 0.3 mL 5% NaNO_2 were placed and mixed thoroughly in a test tube. After 5 min. 0.3 mL 10% AlCl_3 was added. The mixture was incubated at room temperature for 5 min, and then 2 mL of 1 M NaOH was added. After 15 min, the resulting mixture was assayed spectrophotometrically at 510 nm. The catechin calibration curve ($0\text{--}100\text{ mg L}^{-1}$) was used to determine the total flavonoid content in each sample, and then the obtained values were recalculated to fresh weight ($\text{mg eq. C } 100\text{ g}^{-1}\text{ FW}$).

Total antioxidant capacity estimation

The ferric-reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay was used to estimate the total antioxidant capacity [13]. FRAP reagent was prepared by mixing 50 ml of 0.3 mol L^{-1} acetate buffer ($\text{pH} = 3.6$), 5 ml of 10 mmol L^{-1} TPTZ (2,4,6-tripyridyl-s-triazine), and 5 ml of 20 mmol L^{-1} $\text{FeCl}_3 \times 6\text{ H}_2\text{O}$. 80 μL of extract, 240 μL of distilled water, and 2000 μL of FRAP reagent were mixed thoroughly in a test tube. After 10 min, the resulting mixture was assayed spectrophotometrically at 595 nm. The $\text{FeSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calibration curve ($0\text{--}2\text{ mmol L}^{-1}$) was used to determine the total antioxidant capacity in each sample, and then the obtained values were recalculated to fresh weight ($\text{mmol Fe}^{2+} 100\text{ g}^{-1}\text{ FW}$).

Statistical analysis

All assays were performed in triplicates, and the results were expressed as the mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). SPSS 22.0 software package program (IBM, SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) was used for the analysis of variance (ANOVA) with a least significant difference (LSD) test for pairwise comparisons. Statistical significance was achieved at the $p \leq 0.05$ level for differences in means between treatments.

RESULTS

Effects of drought on plant growth parameters

This study showed that the drought strongly limited the growth of studied plants. However, the effect of drought was not the same for each plant species. On the one hand, the growth parameters, including plant height and leaf area in basil and oregano plants, were significantly lower under moderate (drought at 60% WHC) than those recorded under mild drought conditions (drought at 80% WHC), as indicated in Table 1. On the other hand, no significant difference in plant height and leaf area was detected between moderate and mild drought conditions in the case of hyssop and mint plants, indicating that the effect of drought on the plant growth parameters is species-dependent.

Table 1. Effects of drought on plant growth parameters

Plant species	Treatment*	Plant height (cm)	Above ground biomass		Leaf area (cm ²)
			Fresh weight (g per plant)	Dry weight (g per plant)	
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L. (basil)	T1 (90% WHC)	44.3 \pm 6.9 ^a	34.9 \pm 4.1 ^a	3.3 \pm 0.3 ^a	7.2 \pm 0.4 ^{a**}
	T2 (80% WHC)	46.7 \pm 6.1 ^a	35.9 \pm 4.6 ^a	3.2 \pm 0.4 ^a	7.3 \pm 0.5 ^a
	T3 (60% WHC)	36.6 \pm 6.8 ^b	28.9 \pm 3.1 ^b	2.8 \pm 0.3 ^b	6.3 \pm 0.5 ^b
	T4 (40% WHC)	32.5 \pm 5.1 ^b	27.5 \pm 3.5 ^b	2.7 \pm 0.3 ^b	5.3 \pm 0.6 ^c
	LSD _{0.05}	6.23	3.91	0.34	0.52
<i>Hyssopus officinalis</i> L. (hyssop)	T1 (90% WHC)	22.2 \pm 1.6 ^a	55.1 \pm 4.9 ^a	7.7 \pm 0.2 ^a	0.7 \pm 0.1 ^a
	T2 (80% WHC)	21.1 \pm 2.1 ^a	55.3 \pm 2.2 ^a	7.8 \pm 0.3 ^a	0.6 \pm 0.0 ^a
	T3 (60% WHC)	21.0 \pm 1.3 ^a	54.8 \pm 1.6 ^a	7.7 \pm 0.4 ^a	0.6 \pm 0.1 ^a
	T4 (40% WHC)	18.2 \pm 2.2 ^b	38.1 \pm 2.7 ^b	5.9 \pm 0.6 ^b	0.5 \pm 0.1 ^b
	LSD _{0.05}	1.72	3.85	0.61	0.05
<i>Origanum vulgare</i> L. (oregano)	T1 (90% WHC)	31.9 \pm 3.7 ^a	43.5 \pm 2.5 ^a	4.4 \pm 0.3 ^a	4.5 \pm 0.3 ^a
	T2 (80% WHC)	30.6 \pm 3.1 ^a	41.3 \pm 4.9 ^a	4.1 \pm 0.5 ^a	4.3 \pm 0.3 ^a
	T3 (60% WHC)	26.9 \pm 3.3 ^b	35.7 \pm 3.1 ^b	3.7 \pm 0.4 ^b	3.8 \pm 0.3 ^b
	T4 (40% WHC)	24.3 \pm 3.5 ^b	33.9 \pm 2.1 ^b	3.5 \pm 0.3 ^b	3.6 \pm 0.2 ^b
	LSD _{0.05}	3.3	3.14	0.35	0.28
<i>Mentha x piperita</i> L. (mint)	T1 (90% WHC)	22.3 \pm 1.2 ^a	16.5 \pm 1.3 ^a	1.7 \pm 0.1 ^a	3.9 \pm 0.5 ^a
	T2 (80% WHC)	21.3 \pm 2.6 ^a	15.8 \pm 1.9 ^{ab}	1.6 \pm 0.2 ^a	3.7 \pm 0.6 ^{ab}
	T3 (60% WHC)	20.7 \pm 1.5 ^a	15.1 \pm 0.8 ^b	1.6 \pm 0.1 ^a	3.5 \pm 0.6 ^{bc}
	T4 (40% WHC)	18.0 \pm 1.3 ^b	12.7 \pm 1.1 ^c	1.3 \pm 0.2 ^b	3.1 \pm 0.4 ^c
	LSD _{0.05}	1.67	1.27	0.17	0.52

*Treatment: (T1) optimum watering - 95% of substrate water holding capacity; (T2) mild stress - 80% of substrate water holding capacity; (T3) moderate stress - 60% of substrate water holding capacity; and (T4) severe stress - 40% of substrate water holding capacity

**Values marked with different letters in the same column indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$)

The results of this study also showed that drought negatively impacted the above-ground biomass of the studied plants. Compared to the non-stress treatment, severe drought conditions

showed a 22.1%, 23%, 26.9%, and 30.9% fresh weight reduction in oregano, mint, basil, and hyssop plants, respectively. A similar decreasing trend was observed in the dry weight.

With respect to biomass production, it is worth mentioning that hyssop plants produced the highest fresh and dry weight, followed by oregano plants grown under conditions with the highest water availability (control treatment). It is also interesting to note that plant height, leaf area, and above-ground biomass for each studied plant species did not differ significantly between non-stress and mild drought stress conditions.

Effects of drought on antioxidant properties of plant extracts

The total phenolic and flavonoid content in leaves of all studied plant species was greater under moderate and severe drought conditions compared to control (non-stress) treatment. The same trend was also observed for total antioxidant capacity (Table 2). These results strongly suggest that drought can trigger the plant defense systems, resulting in the enhanced production of phenolic and flavonoid compounds.

Table 2. *Effects of drought on antioxidant properties of plants*

Plant species	Treatment*	Total phenolics (mg 100 g ⁻¹ FW)	Total flavonoids (mg 100 g ⁻¹ FW)	Antioxidant capacity (mmol Fe ²⁺ 100 g ⁻¹)
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L. (basil)	T1 (90% WHC)	140.3 ± 5.1 ^{b**}	42.7 ± 3.0 ^c	1.02 ± 0.05 ^b
	T2 (80% WHC)	146.3 ± 5.9 ^b	43.8 ± 2.2 ^{bc}	1.04 ± 0.04 ^b
	T3 (60% WHC)	163.2 ± 14.9 ^a	46.3 ± 2.9 ^a	1.11 ± 0.03 ^a
	T4 (40% WHC)	158.4 ± 5.1 ^a	45.4 ± 2.3 ^{ab}	1.10 ± 0.05 ^a
	LSD _{0.05}	8.45	2.36	0.046
<i>Hyssopus officinalis</i> L. (hyssop)	T1 (90% WHC)	80.0 ± 6.1 ^c	38.9 ± 3.1 ^b	0.95 ± 0.08 ^b
	T2 (80% WHC)	88.6 ± 3.0 ^b	37.2 ± 5.5 ^b	0.91 ± 0.09 ^b
	T3 (60% WHC)	111.9 ± 5.1 ^a	45.3 ± 3.2 ^a	1.43 ± 0.14 ^a
	T4 (40% WHC)	107.6 ± 4.9 ^a	45.7 ± 3.0 ^a	1.41 ± 0.13 ^a
	LSD _{0.05}	4.98	4.31	0.12
<i>Origanum vulgare</i> L. (oregano)	T1 (90% WHC)	223.8 ± 14.7 ^c	123.3 ± 5.1 ^b	1.66 ± 0.5 ^c
	T2 (80% WHC)	253.2 ± 20.1 ^b	132.5 ± 4.6 ^a	1.92 ± 0.3 ^b
	T3 (60% WHC)	285.1 ± 16.8 ^a	135.2 ± 3.5 ^a	2.49 ± 0.3 ^a
	T4 (40% WHC)	276.2 ± 12.6 ^a	134.5 ± 4.4 ^a	2.41 ± 0.3 ^a
	LSD _{0.05}	17.1	4.43	0.34
<i>Mentha x piperita</i> L. (mint)	T1 (90% WHC)	363.8 ± 16.5 ^b	211.2 ± 4.3 ^b	3.19 ± 0.04 ^b
	T2 (80% WHC)	364.7 ± 22.1 ^b	213.2 ± 5.7 ^b	3.21 ± 0.05 ^b
	T3 (60% WHC)	392.9 ± 19.9 ^a	219.9 ± 5.6 ^a	3.35 ± 0.10 ^a
	T4 (40% WHC)	385.4 ± 20.1 ^a	218.1 ± 2.8 ^a	3.33 ± 0.21 ^a
	LSD _{0.05}	18.2	4.71	0.11

*Treatment: (T1) optimum watering - 95% of substrate water holding capacity; (T2) mild stress - 80% of substrate water holding capacity; (T3) moderate stress - 60% of substrate water holding capacity; and (T4) severe stress - 40% of substrate water holding capacity

**Values marked with different letters in the same column indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$)

Study results also suggest that plants' total antioxidant capacity, total phenolics, and total flavonoids were strongly correlated. In this study, there was no significant difference in total phenolic and flavonoid content within each tested plant species, comparing non-stress and mild drought stress conditions, as indicated in Table 2. The highest total phenolic contents (392.9 mg 100 g⁻¹), total flavonoid contents (219.9 mg 100 g⁻¹), and total antioxidant capacity through FRAP assay (3.35 mmol Fe²⁺ 100 g⁻¹) were observed in mint plants exposed to drought at 60% WHC.

DISCUSSION

Drought is widely acknowledged as the most significant abiotic factor affecting plant growth, development, and productivity. The negative effects of drought on plant growth are usually perceived as a decline in plant height, aboveground biomass (both fresh and dry weight), and leaf size, as evidenced by numerous research studies [14, 15, 16]. Farooq et al. [17] reported that drought impacts plant growth by causing a variety of morpho-anatomical and biochemical changes, primarily aimed at reducing water loss through transpiration. A decline in plant growth is one of the foremost responses of plants to drought, according to this point of view.

Several studies have demonstrated that a decline in plant growth is more pronounced as the drought conditions worsen [18, 19, 20]. These observations are reflected in the results of this study. In this study, the highest values for plant height, fresh and dry weight, and leaf area were recorded in well-watered plants (control treatment). In contrast, the lowest values were observed in plants exposed to severe drought stress conditions, regardless of plant species. These results strongly indicate that drought duration is one of the main factors influencing plant behavior under drought conditions.

It is interesting to note that in this study, there was no significant difference in the growth parameters investigated between mild drought stress and control treatment, regardless of the plant species. Considering that a decline in plant growth is a reliable indicator of drought stress, it can be concluded that the investigated plants tolerate short-term drought conditions well.

The impact of drought on plant growth depends not only on the drought severity and duration but also on the plant species, that is, on its defense mechanisms against drought [21]. Some drought-defense mechanisms can be attributed to plant morpho-anatomical adjustments, and some to physiological and biochemical reactions within the plant [22]. Numerous studies have revealed that plants activate a wide range of physiological reactions, including the biosynthesis of phenolic compounds when subjected to drought [23, 24, 25]. Phenolic compounds serve plants as scavengers of reactive oxygen species (ROS), alleviating oxidative stress, which accompanies drought [26]. Therefore, plants tend to increase the biosynthesis of phenolic compounds under drought stress conditions, and the results of this study strongly support this hypothesis. This study revealed that plants exposed to drought had higher levels of total phenolics than those with adequate water supply (control treatment). For example, in mint, basil, hyssop, and oregano plants exposed to moderate drought conditions (drought at 60% WHC), the total phenolic content was about 7.5%, 14%, 21.5%, and 28.5% higher than in well-watered plants, respectively. Similar results have also been reported in other studies for a number of aromatic plant species [27, 28]. These results could be of particular importance to both herbal producers and biopharmaceutical companies, given the fact that most phenolic compounds have therapeutic value or can be precursors for drug development. Indeed, the quality of aromatic and medicinal plants can be significantly improved by deliberately applying drought stress during their cultivation, and numerous scientists confirm this [29, 30]. However, it should be mentioned that drought reduces the biomass production of aromatic plants, which indicates that in the cultivation of aromatic plants, special attention must be paid to the interference of these two different drought stress-related effects [31]. Modifying the irrigation schedule and controlling the amount of water used are certainly excellent approaches to increase the quality of aromatic plants without negative effects on plant biomass production.

This study also found that the total phenolic content in leaves of all studied plant species was lower in plants exposed to severe drought conditions than in plants exposed to moderate stress conditions. Numerous studies also demonstrated that prolonged drought stress can substantially inhibit the synthesis of phenolic compounds in plants [32, 33]. The decrease in the synthesis of phenolic compounds in plants under severe drought conditions can be attributed to the detrimental effects of prolonged drought on the shikimate/phenylpropanoid

pathway, thereby limiting the plants' ability to biosynthesize these metabolites under such circumstances [34, 35]. Prolonged drought is thought to reduce the activity of enzymes involved in the phenylpropanoid pathway, thereby decreasing the production of phenolic compounds. Severe water scarcity can also dramatically reduce photosynthetic capacity, which alters carbon allocation and plant metabolism, often resulting in lower concentrations of shikimate/phenylpropanoid pathway intermediates and, thus, phenolic compounds.

In this study, the total flavonoid content in leaves of the studied plants followed a similar pattern as the total phenolic content, regardless of the drought treatment. Given the fact that flavonoids are among the most abundant phenolic compounds in plants, these results were expected.

The study results also demonstrated that drought increased the total antioxidant capacity in the leaves of all studied plants compared to well-watered plants. This increase was more pronounced under moderate and severe drought stress than under control and mild drought stress. The same tendency was also observed for total phenolic and flavonoid contents, indicating that phenolic compounds are among the most important substances in strengthening the total antioxidant capacity of plants.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study point to the conclusion that the quality of aromatic plants can be improved significantly by deliberately applying drought stress during their cultivation, particularly from the point of view of increasing the antioxidant properties of plants. Controlling the amount of water used and adjusting irrigation schedules are certainly excellent approaches to improve the quality of aromatic plants without affecting plant biomass production when water stress is deliberately applied.

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